

Percentage of spikelet sterility induced by high temperature under natural climatic condition in southeastern Sichuan, China.

Method	Daily mean temperature (°C)	Daily maximum temperature (°C)	Sterility (%)	Spikelets or panicles observed (no.)
Spikelet treatment	27.9 ± 1.02	32.4 ± 1.75	7.24 ± 1.64	11,984
	31.27 ± 1.12	36.35 ± 1.11	10.85 ± 2.05	7,719
Panicle treatment	27.2 ± 1.10	31.35 ± 2.39	14.87 ± 2.84	200
	30.87 ± 0.06	35.27 ± 0.25	21.93 ± 1.36	150

indicate that daily mean temperatures 30 °C or lower and daily maximum temperatures 35 °C or lower significantly affected spikelet sterility.

To determine the stages most sensitive to high temperature, we treated 2,636

spikelets at meiosis, 778 at pollen grain development stage, and 1,320 at flowering, using 35 °C for 4 h in the phytotron. This induced 4.1% sterility at meiosis, 5.3% at pollen grain development, and 15.8% at flowering.

The index of heat tolerance (% fertility at high temperature/ % sterility at normal temperature) for hybrid rices Shan You 2 and Ai You 2 were determined at 33, 35, and 37 °C in the phytotron. Heat tolerance for Shan You 2 was 1.05, 0.78, and 0.14; that for Ai You 2 was 0.84, 0.42, and 0.09, respectively. Thus Shan You 2 tolerated high temperature better than did Ai You 2.

Adopting high temperature-tolerant varieties and adjusting flowering times are strategies to avoid high temperature sterility. □

Adverse soils tolerance

Modified screening method for salt tolerance

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We developed a practical method to screen rice varieties for salt tolerance, based on IRRI's screening techniques. Some modifications have been made:

1. Rice seedlings are planted in soil fertilized with NPK instead of raised in solution culture, simplifying the screening of more varieties at lower cost.
2. Screening is fixed at the 3-leaf stage to eliminate the unfavorable effects caused by 2-wk-old seedlings grown in different seasons.

3. At 4 wk after transplanting (WT) the plants are scored by both the percentage of dead leaves and the salt injury symptoms (visual), and IRRI's standard of score 2 and score 1 are merged into score 1.

We have tested 1,580 rice varieties, including some of IRRI's resistant and susceptible checks such as Nona Bokra, Pokkali, Kalarata, and Damodar, by this modified method. Results are similar to those with IRRI's technique. The procedure is as follows:

- Germinate rice seeds in demineralized water.
- Plant the pregerminated seeds in soil fertilized with NPK.
- Irrigate up to 1 cm depth until seedlings reach the 3-leaf stage.
- Pull the seedlings without injuring the roots, wash the roots in water, and select

four good uniform seedlings from each variety.

- Plant them in a tray (41 × 27 × 13 cm) filled with 7 kg clay loam soil, and add 5.6 liters of 0.5% common salt solution to the soil. The ECE of the soil saturation extract should be 8-10 dS/m. Plant tolerant and susceptible checks.
- Add demineralized water whenever necessary.
- Score at 4 WT, using percentage of dead leaves and leaf injury symptoms (see table). □

Results of screening rice plants for tolerance for salinity, using a modified method. CNRRI, China, 1988.

Dead leaves ^a (%)	Reaction to salinity	Score	Tolerance degree
0-35	Normal growth, absence of salinity symptoms	1	Highly tolerant
36-50	Restricted growth and tillering, a few rolling leaves	3	Tolerant
51-70	Very restricted growth and tillering, most leaves rolling	5	Moderately tolerant
71-90	Growth ceases, most leaves and some plants dead	7	Moderately susceptible
91-100	Most plants dead or nearly dead	9	Susceptible

^aPercentage dead leaves = $\frac{\text{no. of dead leaves/plant}}{\text{no. of leaves/plant}} \times 100$.

Rice yield responses in a saline soil in Sri Lanka

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In the low country wet zone of Sri Lanka, 10% of riceland is coastal saline. Pokkali is one of the few adaptable varieties, particularly where soil conductivity goes up to 7-8 dS/m. However, Pokkali is not widely grown because it has low yields and is susceptible to lodging and diseases.

This study compared two promising salt-tolerant cultivars with Pokkali at 2 spacings in 1985-86 wet season in a farmer's field with salinity up to about 7 dS/m.

Two-week-old seedlings of Bw 272-8, Bw 297-2, and Pokkali from a dry bed

nursery were planted at 3 seedlings/ hill, spaced 15 × 10 cm and 15 × 20 cm. Plot size was 6 × 3 m, with 30 cm space between plots. A 3 × 2 factorial, randomized complete block design with three replications was used.

Fertilizer and agrochemicals were applied as recommended by the Department of Agriculture. Plots were harvested after removing 2 rows around each plot, and yield estimated at 14% moisture.

Soil samples were randomly collected weekly for measuring soil pH and soil conductivity from planting to grain filling.

Highest conductivity was 6.65 dS/m when the crop was at tiller initiation.

Bw 272-8 and Pokkali had some scorching of leaf blade tips. Bw 297-2 had leaf rolling.

Heavy rains 3 to 5 wk after transplanting reduced soil conductivity, which gradually increased to 4 dS/m at flowering stage. No growth retardation or panicle sterility was observed.

Pokkali lodged (40-55%) at flowering, especially in 15- × 10-cm plots. Bw 297-2 lodged slightly in the closer spacing.

Bw 272-8 yielded significantly more than Bw 297-2, and both varieties bested Pokkali (see table). For all varieties, reducing spacing from 15 × 20 cm to 15 × 10 cm significantly increased yield.

Interaction between variety and spacing was not statistically significant.

Effect of spacing on yield of 3 transplanted varieties in saline fields. Bombuwela, Sri Lanka.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)		Variety mean
	15 × 10 cm	15 × 20 cm	
Bw 272-8	3.4	2.7	3.1
Bw 297-2	2.8	2.0	2.4
Pokkali	1.3	0.8	1.1
Spacing mean	2.5	1.9	–

LSD for variety
(0.01) – 0.7 t/ha
(0.05) – 0.5 t/ha

LSD for spacing
(0.01) – 0.6 t/ha

Results show that using resistant varieties at reduced spacing could increase yields in saline tracts. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

Nepal releases nine rice varieties

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Most Nepal ricefields (88%) lie in the tropical to subtropical climatic region that includes the Tarai region (southern plain area), 9.5% are in the midhill region up to 1,372 m, and 2.5% are in cold high hills between 1,372 and

2,316 m. Rice is cultivated up to elevations of 3,048 m.

Nepal's target rice production is 5.1 million t, averaging 3.5 t/ha, by year 2000. Improved varieties are needed to help reach this goal.

In Aug 1987, Nepal released nine varieties for different ecological regions and conditions (see table). Palung 2 is

New rice varieties recommended for ecological regions of Nepal, 1987.

Ecological region and conditions for cultivation	Recommended variety name	Original designation	Parents	Country of origin	When introduced in Nepal	Growth duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Grain type
<i>Temperate region</i>								
For high hills (1524-1981 m) (cold temperate region) Irrigated condition	Palung 2	NR10073-167-3-1-3	BG94-2/Pokhareli Masino		Nepal bred	158-186	4.9 - 7.2	Coarse
For midhills (914-1524 m)	Khumal 2	NR10068-60-3-2	Jarneli/KN-LB-36t BLK-2-8	Nepal	Nepal bred	130-153	3.5 - 7.7	Coarse
Warm temperate region	Khumal 4	NR10078-76-14	IR28/Pokhareli Masino	Nepal	Nepal bred	139-148	4.2 - 8.4	Coarse
<i>Tropical to subtropical region</i>								
1) Irrigated condition (610-1524 m) Early season (Feb-Jun) cultivation (Chaite Dhan Kheti)	Chaite 2	IR7151-260-3-3	BG34-8/IR2061-522-6-9 (IRRI)		1979	120-125	3.6 - 6.4	Medium
	Chaite 4	IR9729-67-3	BG34-8/IR28//IR2095-625-1-252 (IRRI)		1980	120-125	3.4 - 6.6	Medium
Normal season (Jun-Oct) cultivation (Barkhe Dhan Kheti)	Barkhe 2 Khajura 2	B4416-126-3-21 PAU41-262	C4-63 GB/B 531b-TK-39 RP72/Mutant 65	Indonesia India	1977 1979	130-140 135-145	3.5 - 5.3 3.3 - 4.7	Fine Medium
2) Rainfed lowland condition For normal season cultivation	Makwanpur 1	BG400-1	Ob 78/IR20/H4	Sri Lanka	1980	140-150	3.5 - 6.3	Coarse
3) Rainfed upland condition For normal season cultivation	Ghaiya 2	MW10	MTU/W. Kakaiku	India	1980	110-115	2.1 - 4.7	Medium